

An Empirical Analysis of Influence of Social Media on Voters' Choices during the Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Elections in Edo State

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Abstract

Media and communication are essential components of democracy. Media platform can be electronic, visual or social and are drivers of democratic deepening as well as instrumental to grooming anarchy on the other hand. In other words, there have been sustained debates among shades of opinion on the actual role social media play in electoral politics and democratic sustainability. Whereas social media has acted as catalyst for popular mobilization for political engagement it has also created platforms for mobilizing its teeming audience for rebellion and disruption of democratic order at some points such as Nigeria's experience with the infamous EndSars Protests of 2020. The paper explored the Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT) as its theoretical framework. To achieve its set objective, a sample of 240 registered voters was taken using purposive and convenience sampling techniques to draw sample of 40 respondents from six selected local government areas across the three senatorial districts of Edo State for the purpose of questionnaires administration. In addition to the questionnaires administered. The hypothesis of the study was tested using chi square analysis. This paper found that social media platforms were powerful tools in the rapid dissemination of political information throughout the Nigeria's electoral process of 2023 acting as critical conduits for political discourse, enabling the swift transmission of information to a broader audience. The paper further established an association between the frequency of social media interactions involving political contents and voters' preferences during the 2023 presidential elections among the voters in Edo State. This paper recommends that Edo State government should provide incentives towards open and free media access down to the communities' level to increase the prominence of social media as an information-sharing platform so as to engender the possibility of a more inclusive and engaged citizenry and robust voter participation as a remedy to perennial voter apathy. It was concluded that social media did not only booster voter participation but shape electoral outcomes during the 2023 presidential elections and that the influence cut across distinct demographic, social, economic and cultural spectrum.

Keywords: Democracy, Elections, Media, Presidential Elections, Social Media, Voters' choices

Introduction

The use of new social media in politics has continued to grow in many parts of Africa since the 21st century. The role of social media networks such as mobile phones' SMS, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube in deepening the democratization of Nigeria in recent times cannot be overemphasized. For example, 2019 elections witnessed a massive use of mobile phones' SMS, Facebook, Twitter in the general elections in Nigeria. The social media networks like Facebook, Twitter and YouTube are amongst the most visited websites in Nigeria. Due to their participatory, interactive and cost-effective nature, they have become veritable instruments for carrying out election campaigns and other

electioneering activities, political engagement and mobilization among others (Oladimeji, 2023).

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, has a complex political history characterized by democratic transitions, military rule, and socioeconomic challenges. The 2023 presidential elections marked another significant milestone in the country's democratic trajectory, as citizens exercised their constitutional rights to elect leaders who will shape the nation's future. While existing research acknowledges the growing role of social media in shaping political outcomes globally, there is a paucity of in-depth studies that specifically investigate its influence on voters' behaviour within specific states in Nigeria. The 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria, spanning federal, state, and local levels, present an opportune moment to explore the dynamics of social media influence on voters' choices in Edo State in particular.

Edo State, known for its politically conscious population and active civic engagement, offers an intriguing setting for examining the interplay between social media engagement and electoral decisions during the last presidential elections held on February 25 2023. Located in the south-south region, Edo State is known for its rich cultural heritage, vibrant politics, and diverse socioeconomic dynamics. The State's political significance, coupled with the spiraling influence of social media formed the base of this study. Edo State's political landscape is characterized by a multi-party system, vibrant political campaigns, and deeply rooted voter loyalties. The state has historically been a political battleground, with frequent shifts in power dynamics between major parties.

Lastly, by scrutinizing the role of social media in shaping voters' choices during the 2023 presidential elections, this research aimed at contributing insights to the broader discourse on the democratization process in Nigeria. Therefore, the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria were held against the backdrop of a nation striving for political and social stability and this study offered a unique opportunity to examine the intricate relationship between influence of social media and voters' choices in Edo State during that election.

It is widely held notion that social media has the possibility of being misused during election because the crowd-source technique it uses are from local communities who are sometimes with partisan interests and biases. Similarly, the platforms are often used to give false information, abuse, and incite violence, thus, social media advantage in promotion of democracy and electoral harmony became more of a contentious discourse. It is in the light of this that the paper investigated the ways and extent to which social media engagement influenced voters' choices during the presidential elections in Edo State. Whereas it is implied that since the ingredients of democracy include freedom of expression, association and freedom of speech as part of fundamental rights entrenched in the 4th Schedule of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria (as amended). Thus, social media engagements should be allowed to fester without hindrance; but such democratic rights should not amount to infringement of the rights of other citizens and political actors within the same democratic space.

Methodology

This paper adopted survey method for data collection and quantitative method of Chi Square in analyzing its findings based on the assessment of the influence of social media engagements on voters' behaviour during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo

State. The survey instrument adopted is questionnaire aimed at eliciting relevant information from respondents. In analysing the data collected, quantitative data was presented using descriptive statistics of frequency tables and analysis of the hypothesis was carried out using the inferential statistical method of Chi-square.

Literature Review

According to Mackenzie (1968), elections are ritual of choices and that their binding character are derived from the participation of the individual as a chooser in a social act which offers legitimate authority in the person chosen. Mackenzie recognizes the importance of elections as legitimizing the power of elected individuals. It also enables the citizens to participate in the political affairs in their respective polities by exercising their franchise rights to choose candidates of their choice. One of the possible shortcomings of this definition was that, it failed to acknowledge the tendency at which elections can be marred by irregularities which consequently usurp the power of the individual voters and thus create questions on the legitimacy of elected office holders.

However, Huntington (1991) submitted that, election has great importance in all democratic regimes because it facilitates the competitive choice of principal officers of government and enables political participation of the bulk of the population in any given society. Democratic systems thus have a common institutional core that establishes their identity and from where they derive their legitimacy. Thus, he signifies the fundamental aspects of election which include: one, it allows candidates to compete under different political parties' platforms by wooing voters to vote for them. Second, it also differentiates the type of political systems – democratic or dictatorial regimes and the source of the former legitimacy.

Dahl (1971) defined elections as "polyarchic contests," highlighting their role in determining who governs in a pluralistic society. For him, elections serve as a means of access to political offices and are indicative of a democratic society's distribution of power. He further asserted that elections serve as a means of access to political offices and are indicative of a democratic society's distribution of power. He emphasized the concept of "inclusion" in elections, where all eligible citizens have the opportunity to participate in the decision-making process through regular and free elections. Dahl's definition emphasizes not just the act of voting but also the importance of political equality and genuine competition among various political options.

On social media, Boyd and Ellison (2007) cited in Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023) described it as "a web-based service that allows individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system." This definition emphasizes the interactive nature of social media platforms and their role in enabling users to connect, communicate, and share information within their networks. Typical examples of social media platforms, as defined by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), include applications like Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Flickr, 2go, and Youtube, as well as interactive features on these platforms like retweeting on Twitter, commenting on Facebook, and sharing on Whatsapp. These instruments are referred to as media since they are tools that may also be employed for information storage and transmission. Unlike traditional media such as television and radio, however, most social media platforms allow its users to communicate and share information freely, as well as express their opinions on the World Wide Web at their leisure.

According to Campbell et al (2011) cited in Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023), it is much more about what people do with technology than the technology itself, because rather than simply retrieving information, users are now creating and consuming it, and thus adding value to the websites that allow them to do so. Web 2.0 has progressed from merely retrieving information to interaction, interoperability, and collaboration. Sinclair and Vogus (2011) described social media as a broad term that describes software tools that create user generated content that can be shared." However, some basic features are required for a website to meet the requirements of a social network website: the site must contain user profiles, content, a method for users to connect with one another and post comments on each other's pages, and join virtual groups based on common interests such as fashion or politics.

Lastly, Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023) opined that the role of social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp, has grown exponentially in political discourse. These platforms have emerged as powerful tools for political communication, enabling candidates and parties to reach a wide audience instantly. However, the impact of social media on voters' decision-making processes remains relatively unexplored, particularly within the context of states such as Edo. While social media offers numerous benefits, it also introduces challenges and potential negative consequences. The spread of misinformation, echo chambers, and online manipulation are concerns that need to be addressed.

Theoretical Review

This paper predicated on Uses and Gratification theory as the theoretical perspective for analyzing the core objective of the paper. Coined in the early 1940s by Katz and Blumer (1974), the Uses and Gratifications Theory was initially developed as an alternative to the traditional "effects" models of communication. Instead of focusing solely on how media content influences audiences, UGT shifts the focus towards the audience's active role in selecting and interpreting media content based on their psychological and social needs. Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch refined the theory over the years, suggesting that individuals use media to satisfy specific needs, including cognitive, affective, personal integrative, social integrative, and tension release needs (Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo, 2023).

Applying the Uses and Gratification Theory as theoretical framework. Social media platforms, with their diverse content and interactive features, have provided fertile ground for the application of UGT. Individuals engage with social media for various reasons, aligning with the theory's core principles of seeking specific gratifications. One primary cognitive need met by social media is the acquisition of information. Users turn to platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram to stay informed about current events, industry trends, or even personal updates from friends and family. The abundance of user-generated content empowers individuals to curate their information sources, thus enabling the satisfaction of their cognitive needs (Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo, 2023).

Empirical Analysis of Influence of Social Media on Voters' Decisions during the Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Elections in Edo State Table 1: Analysis of Copies of the Questionnaires Retrieved

LGAs	Copies Administered	Copies Retrieved	Percentage
Akoko Edo	40	39	98.0
Esan Central	40	37	92.5
Esan North East	40	37	92.5
Etsako Central	40	38	95.0
Ovia North East	40	38	95.0
Ovia South West	40	37	92.5
Total	240	226	94.2

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 2: Are you familiar with social media?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	226	100%
No	0	0%
No Response	0	0%
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 3: How frequently do you use social media platforms?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Multiple times a day	143	63.3
Once a day	48	21.2
A few times a week	31	13.7
Rarely	4	1.8

Never	0	0
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 4: Which social media platforms do you use?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Facebook	71	31.4
Twitter	46	20.4
Instagram	29	12.8
Whatsapp	56	24.8
Tik Tok	24	10.6
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 5: Were you aware of the 2023 General Elections in Edo State?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	226	100
No	0	0
No Response	0	0
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 6: Did you changed your political preferences or opinions based on content you encountered on social media during the 2023 General Elections campaign?

Responses	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	182	80.5
No	38	16.8
No Response	6	2.7

Total	226	100
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Source: Field study (2024)

Table 7: Do you believe that social media interactions play a role in shaping the outcome of the 2023 General Elections?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	136	60.2
No	82	36.3
No Response	8	3.5
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 8: Have you ever encountered information related to a political candidate or an election on social media that later turned out to be false or misleading?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	136	60.2
No	83	36.7
No Response	7	3.1
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

H0: There is no association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 general elections in Edo State.

H1: There is association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 general elections in Edo State.

To test hypothesis with chi square analysis, the responses in tables 6 and 7 were used.

Table 9: Computation of Observed Frequencies

Question No	A	B	C	Total
D	182	36	6	226

E	136	82	8	226
Total	318 (70.4%)	120 (26.5%)	14 (3.1%)	452

Table 10: Calculating Expected Counts from Observed Counts

	A	B	C	Total
D	$226 \times 318 / 452 = 159$	$226 \times 120 / 452 = 60$	$226 \times 14 / 452 = 7$	226
E	$226 \times 318 / 452 = 159$	$226 \times 120 / 452 = 60$	$226 \times 14 / 452 = 7$	226
Total	318	120	14	452

Table 11: Computation of Chi square

	<i>Observed Frequency (O)</i>	<i>Expected Frequency (E)</i>	<i>Deviation (O-E)</i>	<i>Deviation Squared (O-E)²</i>	<i>Squared and Weighed (O-E)²/E</i>
A	182	159	23	529	3.3270
B	38	60	-22	484	8.0666
C	6	7	-1	1	0.1424
D	136	159	-23	529	3.3270
E	82	60	22	484	8.0666
F	8	7	1	1	0.1424
Total	452	452			23.072

Calculated $X^2 = 23.072$, $df = K - 1 = 6 - 1 = 5$, Alpha level = 0.05, Table value = 11.070.

In view of the above computation, chi-square calculated is greater than the table value i.e. $23.073 > 11.070$. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1); in other words, there is significant association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo State.

The period prior to, during and after the 2023 general elections in Nigeria was characterized by social media mobilization for political and election discourses and actions, the impact of social media interactions on voters' attitudes, preferences, and choices takes center stage. The data presented in Table 6 revealed that a substantial 80.3% of respondents claimed to have changed their political preferences or opinions due to content

encountered on social media during the 2023 General Elections campaign. This statistical data underscored the significant influence that social media platforms wield over political discourse and voter behaviour. Traditional media channels have long held the power to shape public opinion, but social media's interactive nature allows for personalized content consumption and the potential for more revolutionary response, fast and decisive.

The fact that 16.8% of respondents reported not changing their political preferences or opinions based on social media content suggests that social media's impact is not uniform across all users. This discrepancy could be attributed to factors such as individual exposure to diverse viewpoints, critical thinking skills, and pre-existing political leanings. However, even this subset of voters that remained unchanged may have still been exposed to political content on social media, even if it did not overtly influence their stance. It's important to consider the role of confirmation bias, where individuals seek out information that aligns with their existing beliefs. This bias could lead to the polarization of opinions as users interact with content that reinforces their viewpoints. Additionally, the 3.3% of respondents who claimed indifference might indicate a level of apathy or scepticism towards the influence of social media on their political attitudes.

Table 7 presented an equally significant finding: 60.2% of respondents believed that social media interactions play a role in shaping the outcome of the 2023 General Elections. This statistic reflects a widespread recognition of social media's potential to sway election results. It suggests that the majority of voters perceive social media as a powerful tool for political engagement and persuasion. Conversely, the 36.3% of respondents who did not believe in the assertion that social media influences election outcomes might hold a more skeptical view of the platform's influence or might have a different understanding of the factors driving electoral results. It's worth considering whether this skepticism stems from concerns over the authenticity of information shared on social media, potential algorithmic biases, or simply a belief in the resilience of traditional campaigning methods. The 1.7% of respondents who provided no answer might signify a lack of awareness about the role of social media in politics, reflecting a need for more comprehensive education and awareness campaigns regarding the influence of online platforms on political processes. But as the responses of the majority of the respondents showed and hypothesis two tested revealed, social media interactions have the potential to impact voters' attitudes, preferences and choices during election.

Exploratory studies done in Nigeria during the 2015 elections indicated that social media played a significant role in turning popular support amongst young voters against the then incumbent federal government. Ijioma and Kogah (2020) argued that the use of social media influence political opinion and voting behaviour and hold that social media, has become vital in Nigerian politics, playing a role in enabling Muhammadu Buhari to win the 2015 Presidential elections. Similarly, Aduloju (2016) noted that youth networks helped to shape the 2015 elections in terms of exposing and preventing insecurity and fraud. By the 2019 presidential election, social media had come of age, and instead of the dominance of that space by young millennial and young adults, we observed that even older people were relying on social media for political information and political debates (Dakuku, 2022).

Thus, as Olowookere and Audu-Bako (2019) aptly captured it, social media is now used to inform and mobilize voters by various stakeholders during elections. It is therefore not surprising that the 2023 General Elections witnessed an unprecedented level of social

media engagement and interaction among voters. This digital era has redefined the dynamics of political communication, giving rise to questions about the extent to which these interactions impact voters' attitudes, preferences, and choices. The frequency of social media interactions related to political content has exhibited a positive correlation with substantial changes in voters' attitudes and preferences. Several mechanisms contributed to the association between the frequency of social media interactions related to political content and changes in voters' attitudes during the 2023 presidential elections. Firstly, the sheer volume of political content available on social media platforms provides voters with a diverse range of perspectives, enabling them to engage with narratives that resonate with their existing beliefs or challenge their viewpoints.

The findings from this study provided valuable insights into the complex relationship between social media interactions and voters' attitudes, preferences, and choices in the context of the 2023 presidential elections. The data underscores the significant influence that social media wields over political discourse and its potential to shape electoral outcomes. Political discussions on social media can quickly escalate and shape public sentiment. During the 2023 Nigeria presidential elections, for instance, hashtags like #NigeriaDecides trended globally on Twitter, reflecting both domestic and international interest in the electoral process. This not only amplified political conversations but also enabled citizens to voice concerns, opinions, and grievances directly to political candidates.

What is evident is that social media played a pivotal role in increased youth participation in the discourse and campaigns. Socio-economic problems, including incessant university strikes and high youth unemployment, apparently contributed to their engagement. The finding of this study also shows that the viral nature of trending topics, hashtags, and posts can amplify certain narratives and influence public discourse. The "bandwagon effect" and "spiral of silence" are psychological phenomena that can contribute to the belief in social media's impact on electoral outcomes. The bandwagon effect suggests that people tend to align with perceived majority opinions, while the spiral of silence theory posits that individuals are more likely to voice their opinions if they believe they align with prevailing societal views. On social media, the prominence of certain political messages can create an illusion of overwhelming consensus, leading users to adopt or reinforce those views.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study embarked on a comprehensive exploration of the symbiotic relationship between social media and voters' choices during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo State, Nigeria. By harnessing the power of agenda-setting theory, social influence theory, and user gratification theory, the study unveiled the transformative impact of social media platforms on the dissemination of political information, the fluidity of voters' attitudes, and the democratization of the electoral process. As Nigeria continues its democratic journey, the insights gleaned from this research underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of the role of social media in shaping political narratives and, consequently, influencing the trajectory of the nation's democracy. The study's findings hold the promise of a more engaged, informed, and participatory electorate, positioning social media as a pivotal player in the ongoing evolution of Nigeria's political landscape. The recommendations of the paper are:

1. There is the need for policymakers to recognize the growing influence of social media in political processes. It is thus important to develop guidelines or regulations that ensure transparency, accuracy, and fairness in political information shared on social media platforms. These regulations could help mitigate the spread of misinformation and ensure a more informed electorate.
2. There should be implementation of media literacy programs at both educational institutions and community levels. These programs can empower voters to critically assess information received from social media, helping them distinguish between reliable sources and misleading content. By fostering media literacy, voters can make more informed decisions.

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